

The Effect of Additives on Conductance of Soap Solution (Anionic Soaps) in Non-Aqueous System

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The present work reports results of some conductometric study of magnesium laurate in a few cosolvent mixtures in order to find out if such data can throw light on cosolvency.

EARLIER, the effect of different organic additives on anionic soap in various solvents and their mixtures from the standpoint of solubility measurements were investigated^{2,3}. The steep rise in the solubility at the optimum mole-ratio of the two cosolvents definitely indicates the existence of some intermolecular type of reaction¹⁻³ between soap and solvent under proper environment as per Winsor's Principle^{4,6,7} of balanced solvation.

Experimental

Lauric Acid of reagent quality was crystallised three times from hot alcohol. The purified sample has m.p. 43°-44°. The sodium soap was prepared by neutralisation in hot alcoholic solution and the corresponding metal soaps were then precipitated by reacting the metallic salt solution in a small quantity of distilled water (taking approximately 4% in excess of the theoretical amount) with hot alcoholic solution of the sodium soap, the latter being added dropwise while the whole medium was continuously stirred preferably at 40° to 50°. The precipitate was filtered on the Buchner and was repeatedly washed with hot distilled water until the filtrate gave negative test for the metal salt used. The samples thus prepared were dried and washed with hot chloroform solution, dried again and ultimately analysed quantitatively by standard methods. The percentage of metal content was as follows: Magnesium Laurate, Found: 5.26% Mg (Calculated 5.3%).

The soap solutions were prepared in the respective solvents by taking a known weight of the soap in a definite volume of the solvent in solubility bottles, shaken in a mechanical shaker for about six hours and filtered to get rid of dust, etc. if any. Soap concentrations are given in grammes per 100 ml. solvent.

The conductance measurements were made at 50 C/Sec, with a bridge employing a visual null point indicator (Philips Model). The conductance cell has platinised Pt-electrodes with cell constant = 0.70 cm⁻¹.

Observations

In the present experiments two soap solutions of the same soap content (weight per unit volume) but in two different solvents were mixed and the conductance of the resulting soap solution was measured. Here Propylene Glycol (PG) is taken as the first solvent and the respective effect of the amines, alkylolamines, hydrocarbons etc. have been studied. The principle is more or less like Job's Method of Continued Variation though strictly speaking it is different from the said principle. One physical parameter, specific conductivity, is being studied at a constant soap concentration in different mole-ratios of the two solvents. Three soap concentrations (e.g., 2%, 1.3% and 0.5%) are plotted on the same graph for a single pair of solvents. The observed results are shown in the Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Results and Discussion

It is obvious from the curves that with increasing concentration of soaps, the conductivity increases as expected; however the increase is less than linear and almost tends to a limit. Thus, the curves (Figs. 1-4) with soap concentrations 2% and 1.3% lie very close to each other, but the curve with soap concentration 0.5% lies considerably below.

The most striking feature of these curves common to all systems is that the conductivity shows a maximum at a mole ratio of about 70 : 30 of propylene glycol : other component. The maximum value at any given soap concentration however, differs from system to system as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1 SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY (OHM⁻¹CM⁻¹) AT 30°

Figs.	Solvent mixture	2% soap	1.3% soap	0.5% soap
1	PG+PIPY	7.2×10^{-5}	6.55×10^{-5}	3.6×10^{-5}
2	PG+MORPHO	2.92×10^{-5}	2.72×10^{-5}	1.55×10^{-5}
3	PG+DEA	2.22×10^{-5}	1.97×10^{-5}	1.32×10^{-5}
4	PG+CHCl ₃	3.12×10^{-5}	2.95×10^{-5}	1.53×10^{-5}

